

ROTTLERIN. PART II.

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The N_2O_3 adduct of rottlerin pentamethyl ether is catalytically reduced to a hydro derivative and also isomerises with alkali to a substance giving strong violet ferric reaction. These products are discussed in the light of Robertson's latest formula for rottlerin. It is concluded that the formula of Robertson *et al* does not satisfactorily explain all the known facts about rottlerin.

In Part I (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1862) we advocated that rottlerin is $C_{27}H_{36}O_7$. Since then we have amended this view (*Current Sci.*, 1938, 6, 333 ; *Chem. Ind.*, 1938, 57, 134) on account of the fact that the oxide described in Part I and nitrous acid addition product are better explained on the basis of a $C_{31}H_{30}O_8$ formula containing five hydroxyl groups.

When the methyl ether of rottlerin (17 g.) is treated with sodium nitrite under the conditions described in experimental sequel a yield of 15.5 g. of the adduct is obtained. This indicates that the product is a simple N_2O_3 addition product and no degradation of the molecule has taken place.

The N_2O_3 adduct (m. p. 209° , decomp.), isomerises to a substance, m. p. $152-53^\circ$, by alcoholic potassium hydroxide. This isomeric substance is soluble in alkali. The dihydro derivative of the nitrosite prepared by the catalytic reduction of the substance, m. p. 209° , also isomerises with alkali to a substance, m. p. 139° . This substance is also formed when the *isonitrosite*, m. p. 153° , is catalytically reduced. The nitrosite, m. p. 209° , can be methylated with alkali and dimethyl sulphate to give a substance, m. p. $192-93^\circ$, which may be a mono- or a dimethyl ether of the original product, m. p. 209° . In this connection we wish to state that both the *isonitrosite* and the dihydro-*isonitrosite* give deep violet colour with ferric chloride. The nitrosite, on the other hand, shows no ferric reaction and is insoluble in cold aqueous alkali. Therefore, the methylation takes place *via* the *isonitroso* stage. To prove this, the *isonitrosite* was independently methylated and the same product (m. p. 193°) was isolated. We attempted to hydrolyse the *isonitrosite* with formaldehyde and alcoholic hydrochloric acid but we were unable to isolate any definite product. We are engaged in bringing about this hydrolysis by other methods.

The *isonitrosite* is not a simple hydrolytic product of the nitrosite as it is unaffected when kept in contact with phosphoryl chloride for 2 hours. If the *isonitrosite* formation was due to simple addition of water we would

expect that *isonitrosite* would be retransformed into the nitrosite under these conditions. If the *isonitrosite* is the oximino form of the nitroso grouping, then also we would expect a Beckmann transformation.

The dihydronitrosite, m. p. 163°, on oxidation with potassium permanganate in acetone solution furnishes a substance crystallising in pale yellow needless m. p. 124°, to which we have provisionally assigned the formula $C_{20}H_{29}O_8N$. It seems that this product is formed by the elimination of a fragment of the original rottlerin molecule.

In Part I (*loc. cit.*) we described a hydrolytic product ($C_{20}H_{22}O_4$) of tetrahydrorottlerin obtained with alcoholic hydrochloric acid. We suggested that this product may be identical with the product obtained by Robertson *et al* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 748) by the hydrolysis of tetrahydrorottlerin with baryta. We have now methylated our product and found it to be identical with dimethyltetrahydrorottlerone described by Robertson *et al* (*loc. cit.*). We obtained a yield of 3.2 g. from 8 g. of tetrahydrorottlerin, whilst Robertson *et al* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 311) record a yield of 5.6 g. from 20 g. by alkaline hydrolysis. These authors have advanced the structure (I) for tetrahydrorottlerone mainly on its degradation to β -phenylpropionic acid and 5:7-dihydroxy-2:2-dimethylchroman.

We are unable to subscribe to the above view of its structure on the following grounds:—

(a) The dimethyl ether of tetrahydrorottlerone does not give any indication of the formation of a pyrrilium salt when saturated with hydrogen chloride in ether with salicylaldehyde.

(b) It has not up to now yielded either a semicarbazone or an oxime.

(c) Rottlerone (II), the hydroxychalkone, should isomerise to the corresponding flavanone.

The other half of the rottlerin molecule is supposed to be joined at the place indicated by the arrow in the formula (I). If rottlerone had the structure

(II) then the N_2O_3 adduct would probably have the structure (III) or an alternative with the NO and NO_2 at the positions marked*. It is possible to get benzaldehyde even if the N_2O_3 had added at the positions marked but provisionally we put the groups NO and NO_2 in the chromene ring for several reasons. The nitrosite would be (III) if rottlerin is (II) with the second half attached at the arrow as Robertson *et al* suppose.

(III)

On this basis, the *isonitrosite* would be the corresponding oximino compound. But since the *isonitrosite* shows a strong violet ferric reaction, therefore in the formation of the *isonitrosite* probably a phenolic hydroxyl is set free. We believe that the chroman ring opens up in the *isonitrosite* formation. Moreover, we have noticed that in the hydrolysis of tetrahydrorottlerin with alcoholic hydrochloric acid, if the reaction is stopped after 8 hours very little tetrahydrorottlerone is formed. The product consists mostly of an acid easily soluble in sodium bicarbonate. Unfortunately this acid is unstable and is difficult to purify. However, if this acid be taken in alcohol and heated with hydrochloric acid for a further period of about 16 hours, a good yield of tetrahydrorottlerone is obtained. Therefore rottlerone is formed from rottlerin *via* an acid. Hence it is most probable that in the rottlerin molecule a suppressed carboxyl occurs in the form of an ester or a lactone grouping.

In Robertson's formula of rottlerin there is no place for such a group. We think that the group $PhCH=CH$ should be removed from the phloroglucinol nucleus and be placed near the chromene ring. The formation of a phenolic *isonitroso* derivative suggests that the oxygen of the chromene ring is set free by alkali and the carboxyl of the lactone re-lactonises with the hydroxyl of the tertiary carbinol. On this basis several alternative structures for rottlerin can be formulated including one in which one of the methyls of the *gem*-dimethyl group could be attached to a $COOH$, but the present indications are that the *gem*-dimethyl group exists as such and the lactone is probably attached to the 3:4 carbon atoms of the chromene ring. We think that the methyl phloroglucinol half is joined to

chromene ring through a

The formation of $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_8\text{N}$ by the oxidation of the dihydronitrosite can be explained by the extrusion of C_{10} and a nitrogen atom from the right hand side of chromene ring.

We are engaged in oxidising dimethylrottlerone with lead tetra-acetate and other oxidising agents. Preliminary oxidation with SeO_2 gave a substance in which the double bond containing PhCH was regenerated as the product gave benzaldehyde with alkali.

In criticism of Robertson's latest formula for rottlerin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 310) we find the following difficulties :—

- (a) No derivatives of rottlerin give any reactions of a ketone.
- (b) No bromoform is formed from rottlerin methyl ether with sodium hypobromite hence there cannot be a $\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_3$ group in the molecule.
- (c) The formation of the benzeneazomethylphloracetophenone (Brockmann and Maier, *Naturwiss.*, 1937, 28, 460) is difficult to visualise unless it is assumed that the diazo complex enters the second half of the rottlerin molecule by detaching the rottlerone half. In our opinion the reaction of diazobenzene chloride with rottlerin is complex, the $\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_3$ group of Brockmann and Maier's product arises through the hydrolysis of the chromene ring.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Action of Nitrous Acid on Rottlerin Pentamethylether.—Rottlerin methyl ether (17 g.), dissolved in acetic acid (255 c.c.) by gentle warming, was treated with powdered sodium nitrite (17 g. at 30° during $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The solution was then heated to 80° for 10 minutes and then diluted with a large volume of water (700-800 c.c.). The precipitated bright yellow solid was collected, dried and triturated with ether (about 100 c.c.) in which a small portion dissolved. The crude insoluble material (m.p. $204\text{--}6^\circ$) weighed 15.5 g. It was crystallised from boiling toluene in pale yellow plates, m.p. $208\text{--}9^\circ$ (decomp.). (Found : C, 63.66, 63.87; H, 6.2, 5.9; N, 4.2, 4.17. $\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{40}\text{O}_{11}\text{N}_2$ requires C, 63.9; H, 5.92; N, 4.14 per cent).

Action of Alkali on the Nitrosite : Formation of the isoNitrosite.—The foregoing nitrosite (2 g.) suspended in alcohol (15 c.c.) was treated with 33% aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (10 c.c.). The solution was

warmed on the steam-bath for 3 minutes and then the alcohol removed in *vacuo*. The dark red solution was diluted with water (80 c.c.) and extracted with ether to remove neutral impurities. The aqueous portion or acidification with concentrated hydrochloric acid furnished a sticky yellow product which crystallised from alcohol in yellow plates, m.p. 153°, yield 1.3 g. This substance gives a violet ferric reaction. (Found : C, 63.57; H, 5.98; N, 4.11. $C_{38}H_{46}O_{11}N_2$ requires C, 63.9; H, 5.92; N, 4.14 per cent).

Methylation of isoNitrosite.—To the foregoing isonitrosite (1 g.) dissolved in methanol (10 c.c.) sodium hydroxide solution (15 c.c. of 80%) and dimethyl sulphate (8 c.c.) were added in small portions alternately. The temperature of the mixture was not allowed to rise. The sticky mass obtained by dilution with water (100 c.c.) was washed with water by decantation and finally crystallised from alcohol in bright yellow plates, m.p. 192-93°, yield 0.6 g. (Found : C, 65.22; H, 6.02; N, 4.03. $C_{37}H_{42}O_{11}N_2$ requires C, 64.35; H, 6.09; N, 4.06. $C_{38}H_{44}O_{11}N_2$ requires C, 64.77; H, 6.25; N, 3.98 per cent).

Action of Alkali on Dihydranitrosite.—The dihydranitrosite (Narang, Ray and Roy, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1864) was treated with alkali as described in the case of the nitrosite except that the alkaline solution was heated on the steam-bath for 10 minutes. The product, isolated as described before, crystallised from alcohol in pale yellow elongated plates, m.p. 139°, yield 2 g. from 2.5 g. of the dihydranitrosite. This substance also gives a deep violet ferric reaction. (Found : C, 63.33; H, 6.12; N, 4.13. $C_{34}H_{42}O_4N_2$ requires C, 63.72; H, 6.19; N, 4.13 per cent). This product can be easily obtained by the reduction of the isonitrosite described before in ethyl acetate with palladium and hydrogen. The use of platonic oxide catalyst under atmospheric pressure also furnished the same product and no perhydro derivative or an amine was formed.

Oxidation of the Dihydranitrosite with Acetone-permanganate.—A solution of the dihydranitrosite (2.5 g.) in acetone (40 c.c.) was added in one lot to a solution of potassium permanganate (1.5 g.) in acetone (50 c.c.) and water (25 c.c.). The mixture was shaken for 1½ hours at 45-50°. The filtrate from the manganese oxide was evaporated and the residue was extracted with ether.

The ethereal solution was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution (1%) and water, dried and then evaporated. The residue was crystallised from alcohol (25 c.c.) in long pale yellow needles, m.p. 124°. (Found : C, 64.6; H, 6.06; N, 2.89. $C_{28}H_{30}O_2N$ requires C, 64.59; H, 6.00; N, 2.89 per cent).

Tetrahydrorotterone.—A mixture of tetrahydrorotterin (8 g.) in alcohol (400 c.c.), hydrochloric acid (d 1.14, 80 c.c.) and water (40 c.c.) was heated for 26 hours. The solution was filtered hot and the insoluble powder, thus obtained, was crystallised from ethyl acetate. On heating for a shorter period, an acidic substance was formed which resisted purification. The yield of the crystallised product is 3.2 g. (For analytical data *vide* Narang, Ray and Roy, *loc. cit.*). The substance gives on methylation a methyl ether, m.p. 102°. (*cf.* Robertson *et al.* *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 311).

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